

Environment-like exposure of free-living stages of *Haemonchus contortus* to albendazole: The intra- and intergeneration stability of altered expression of UDP-glycosyl transferases and ABC-transporters

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HIGHLIGHTS

- *H. contortus* juvenile stages were exposed to traces of ABZ and its metabolites.
- In developed larvae L3, expression of 7 UGTs and Pgps genes was changed.
- Three changed UGTs and Pgps expression persisted in the adult nematodes.
- Four changed UGTs and Pgps expression persisted in the second generation of L3.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Anthelmintic drugs are widespread environmental contaminants, but their impact is still poorly understood. Although contact of parasitic nematode *Haemonchus contortus* with traces of anthelmintic drug albendazole (ABZ) altered the expression and activity of several UDP-glycosyl transferases (UGTs) and P-glycoproteins (Pgps, belonging to ABC-transporters), key enzymes in endogenous and xenobiotic metabolism, it is not known whether these changes will last during the life cycle and pass to the next generations. In the present study simulating the environmental-like exposure, free-living stages of *H. contortus* were exposed or unexposed to a sub-lethal dose of ABZ and its transformation products (ABZs) during L3 development. The L3 served for lambs' infection and obtaining of *H. contortus* adults and eggs, which were again exposed or unexposed to ABZs during L3 development. The expression pattern of UGTs and Pgps was analysed and compared in the first generation of L3, in the adults, and in the second generation of L3. The results showed that ABZs exposition during larvae development altered the expression of several *ugt* and *pgp* genes in L3 and adults. The intrageneration stability of ABZs-evoked changes was observed in the case of three genes, four genes maintained the intergeneration stability. Interestingly, ABZs-induced changes in the expression of some genes became apparent only in the second generation of L3. Taking together, contact of free-living stages of *H. contortus* with traces of ABZs in the environment evokes changes in the expression of certain UGTs and Pgps, with some of these changes being intra- and inter-generation stable.

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1. Introduction

Parasitic infections account for severe problems in livestock production. Among the group of small ruminants parasites, gastrointestinal nematode *Haemonchus contortus*, also known as barber's pole worm, is one of the most prevalent and pathogenic. *H. contortus* has a direct life cycle. Host animals, such as sheep and goats, orally digest the infective third-stage larvae (L3). The parasitic stages of L4 and gonochoric adults are hematophagous and reside in the abomasum. The females lay thousands of eggs which are shed on the pasture with the animal faeces. Under favourable conditions, the eggs hatch into the free-living first, second and third-stage larvae (L1, L2, and L3, resp.). The high fecundity of female worms and short generational intervals provide this parasite developmental plasticity for effective adaptation (Emery et al., 2016). Despite the evolutionary origins of arid areas in sub-Saharan Africa, haemonchosis is now common in almost every climate zone (Besier et al., 2016).

Concerning prophylaxis and treatment of haemonchosis, grazing management, nutrition supplementation, selective breeding, or vaccination are partly helpful, but chemotherapy is still the mainstay (Ehsan et al., 2020; Mravcakova et al., 2019; Teixeira et al., 2019). However, massive administration of anthelmintics and non-compliance with the integrated parasite management led to the rapid spread of *H. contortus* resistance to all anthelmintic classes (Ahuir-Baraja et al., 2021; Arsenopoulos et al., 2021; Vineer et al., 2020; Zajicková et al., 2020). Since haemonchosis causes enormous economic losses, it is essential to identify drug resistance mechanisms and factors contributing to resistance development. In the case of benzimidazole anthelmintics (e.g., albendazole, ABZ), the F200Y mutation of the gene encoding the benzimidazole target β -tubulin is a well-described mechanism of resistance for a long time. However, a later study showed that isolates carrying 90–100% F200Y mutation could vary considerably in their resistance level to benzimidazoles (Yilmaz et al., 2017). On the other hand, SNPs in other codons, specifically 167 and 198, have been identified as contributing to benzimidazole resistance (Barrere et al., 2012; Kotze et al., 2012; Sangster et al., 2018). However, during population-wide allele sequencing, distinct β -tubulin alleles were identified within the population, which persisted despite the removal of benzimidazole-induced selection (Avramenko et al., 2019; Dilks et al., 2020).

In addition to target-site mechanisms mentioned above, also a non-target-site mechanisms might contribute to benzimidazole resistance in nematodes. These mechanisms of resistance can be based on increased deactivation of a drug and its efflux through increased expression and activity of drug-metabolizing enzymes (DMEs). These proteins protect all organisms against the potential negative actions of drugs and other xenobiotics. Nematodes possess a relatively large number of DME genes, much higher than other helminth classes (Matoušková et al., 2016). As a result, nematodes are able to effectively metabolise many anthelmintics to form various types of metabolites (Stuchlíková et al., 2018). In our previous studies, we proved *H. contortus* detoxification of ABZ via glycosylation, with glycosylation being more potent in resistant strains than in susceptible ones (Kellerová et al., 2020b; Matouskova et al., 2018). Furthermore, 32 isoforms of UDP-glycosyltransferases (UGTs), the enzymes responsible for glycosylation, have been identified in the *H. contortus* genome, some with higher expression in *H. contortus* resistant strains (IRE, WR) than in the sensitive strain ISE (Matouskova et al., 2018). In the resistant isolates of *H. contortus*, also increased constitutive expression of efflux drug transporters P-glycoproteins (Pgps) from the ABC-transporters superfamily was detected (Mate et al., 2022; Raza et al., 2015). Moreover, the exposure of *H. contortus* adults and juvenile stages to ABZ (in sublethal concentrations) altered the expression of several UGTs and Pgps (Kellerová et al., 2020a, 2020b).

With the aim to reveal the factors contributing to drug resistance, the circulation of ABZ from excrements from ABZ-treated sheep to soil, fodder plants and to other sheep fed this fodder was tested and proved in

real agricultural conditions (Navratilova et al., 2021). Subsequently, increased UGTs and Pgps expression and increased ABZ deactivation were detected in *H. contortus* adults obtained from sheep fed with clover growing in the field fertilised with the excrements with traces of ABZ and its metabolites than in *H. contortus* adults from control sheep (Dimunova et al., 2022a).

All these results clearly show that traces of ABZ and its metabolites are present in the environment and that contact of *H. contortus* with these contaminants changes the expression and activity of UGTs and Pgps. Nevertheless, it is not known whether the altered expression patterns will last during the life cycle and can be passed to the next generations. The present study aimed to fill this gap by simulating the contact of free-living stages of *H. contortus* with traces of ABZ and its transformation products (all together abbreviated as ABZs) in the environment and analysing the expression pattern of UGTs and Pgps in adults and in the subsequent generation of larvae.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sheep infection, eggs and adults isolation, larvae cultivation

All experimental procedures and sheep stable were evaluated and approved by the Ethics Committee of Faculty of Pharmacy, Charles University and accredited by Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, licences No. 59738/2019- MZE-18134, MZE-53255/2022–13143.

Helminth-free (negative coprological examination) Texel lambs (3–4-month-old males, farm Helvíkovice; East Bohemia), were p.o. infected with water suspension of *H. contortus* L3 (6000 per animal) of the ISE strain (Inbred Susceptible Strain, MHco3 (Roos et al., 2004)). The faeces, collected 4 weeks post-infection, were put on a tray, which was covered with plastic foil to prevent evaporation, and kept at 27 °C for 8–10 days. Then, the faeces were rinsed with tap water which was then filtered through 100 μ m and subsequently 20 μ m mesh sieve in 1L conical measuring beakers, in which larvae were left to settle to the bottom. Clean live larvae were stored at 7 °C in the culture flasks for sheep infection or immediately frozen (–80 °C) in plastic tubes with TriReagent solution prior to RNA isolation.

Six weeks post-infection, the lambs were slaughtered, and the abomasum was removed, kept in warm water (37 °C) and transported to the laboratory, where the adults were harvested using the agar method (van Wyk et al., 1980). The freshly isolated adults were washed in phosphate-buffered saline (pH 7.4, 38 °C) and separated by gender based on the morphological characteristics under a stereo microscope.

2.2. Experimental design, larvae exposure

The design of the experiment is shown in Fig. 1. The fresh faeces collected from two *H. contortus* infected lambs were pooled together and spread onto 3 trays (approx. 500 g of faeces per one tray). The number of eggs was determined from 4 g of faeces by the McMaster method with flotation solution and enumerated microscopically in a McMaster counting chamber. The faeces, containing approx. 4 000 eggs per gram, were sprayed (1 mL of solution/100 g of faeces) with either the water solution of 0.1% DMSO for the control group, or 1 μ M ABZ solution or 5 μ M ABZ solution. ABZ was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Prague, Czech republic) and the stock solutions were prepared as 1 mM and 5 mM in DMSO and then diluted 1000 \times with water. The concentrations of ABZ were chosen to be non-toxic to *H. contortus* eggs/larvae (Silva et al., 2021) and environmentally relevant i.e. to be in the middle of scale between C_{max} for ABZ in ovine faeces (Prchal et al., 2016), and ABZ persistent environmental concentration in soil (Belew et al., 2021). Although the faeces were sprayed with solution of ABZ only, we suppose the substantial ABZ transformation to ABZSO and ABZSO₂ as ABZ is easily oxidized (spontaneously, by bacteria, by *H. contortus* eggs/larvae) (Kellerová et al., 2020a; Lagos et al., 2021). After 8 days, three groups of

the first generation of L3 (G1) were isolated and designated as G1 DMSO, G1 ABZ1 and G1 ABZ5. A portion of each group was put into TriReagent for qPCR analysis.

Then, 6000 of G1 L3 from each group were used for oral infection of sheep (one sheep per one group of larvae) to obtain the first generation of adults (G1 adults) and second generation of larvae (G2 larvae). After 4 weeks, faeces were collected from each sheep separately. Before the exposure, the faeces from infected sheep were mixed with eggs-free faeces to have the similar number (and concentration) of eggs in each tray (500 g of faeces; 4000 eggs per g). The faeces from sheep infected with G1 DMSO larvae were spread in one tray and sprayed with a water solution of 0.1% DMSO. The faeces from sheep infected with G1 ABZ1 larvae were divided and spread in two trays, one was sprayed with the water solution of 0.1% DMSO, the second was sprayed with 1 μ M ABZ solution. The faeces from sheep infected with G1 ABZ5 larvae were spread in two trays, one was sprayed with the water solution of 0.1% DMSO, the second was sprayed with 5 μ M ABZ solution. Approx. 500 g of faeces were put in each tray, the exposure doses were 5 mL of solution (1 mL per 100 g of faeces) for each tray. After 8 days, five groups of G2 larvae were isolated and designated as G2 DMSO, G2 ABZ1-DMSO, G2 ABZ1-ABZ1, G2 ABZ5-DMSO and G2 ABZ5-ABZ5.

2.3. RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis

Three groups of G1 larvae, three groups of G1 adults and five groups of G2 larvae served for RNA isolation. From each group, four biological replicates were prepared, each from 30 000 L3 or 15 adult males (M) or 10 adult females (F) of *H. contortus* in 1 mL of TriReagent® (Molecular Research Centre, OH, USA). The samples were homogenised using the Fast-Prep-24 5G Homogenizer (MP Biomedicals, France) for four 30 s intervals with a speed of 6.5 m/s. The total RNA was extracted using TriReagent according to the manufacturer's protocol, using chloroform and isopropanol in the separation and RNA precipitation phases, respectively. The purity and concentration of RNA (absorbance ratios at wavelengths 260/280 and 260/230) were quantified spectrophotometrically using the Tecan Spark® (Tecan Trading AG, Switzerland). To remove DNA contamination, 4 μ g RNA of each sample were treated with DNase I (NEB, UK) and diluted to a concentration of 0.1 μ g/ μ L.

Complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesised from 0.5 μ g RNA in 20 μ L reactions using random hexamer primers and Protoscript II Reverse

Transcriptase (NEB, UK) following the manufacturer's protocol; cDNA was diluted 10 \times and stored at -20°C until further analysis.

2.4. Quantitative PCR (qPCR)

qPCR analysis was performed using 384-well PCR plates each each biological replicate ($N = 4$) was measured in duplicates using Thermal Cycler; QuantStudio™ 6 Flex Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA) with SYBR Green I detection. The final master mix (8 μ L per well) was prepared from 5 ng cDNA, qPCR Xceed SG 1 step 2 \times Mix Lo-ROX (IAB, Czech Republic) as well as both forward and reverse primers (final concentration 100 nM). The PCR run protocol started with a denaturation step (95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min), followed by 40 cycles of two-step amplification (95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 s, 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 s) with fluorescence measurement at the end of each cycle. A melting curve protocol with a heating rate of 0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ every 30 s from 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was used to investigate the specificity of the qPCR reaction.

Based on our previous publications, we selected resistance-related genes (Dimunova et al., 2022a; Kellerová et al., 2020a). The primer sequences for quantification of nine UGT genes and four P-glycoprotein transcripts were designed in Primer3 software and synthesised by Generi Biotech, Czech Republic (Supplementary Table 1). The specificity of the primers was confirmed by the presence of a single peak in the melting curve analyses, and the efficiency of the primers was calculated from the slope of standard curves obtained from serial dilutions.

2.5. Statistical analysis

The reported data are expressed as the mean \pm SD (four biological replicates of each sample). Relative expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001), the qPCR data were normalized to the geometrical mean of two reference genes stability of which was confirmed (glyceraldehyde-3P-dehydrogenase (*gpd*) and RNA polymerase II large subunit (*ama*) (Lecová et al., 2015); and the data from the exposed samples are displayed relative to respective DMSO controls (set to 1). The statistical significance of gene expression differences between the groups was evaluated using ordinary one-way ANOVA with *post-hoc* Holm-Sidak's test ($N = 4$), the significance of the results is displayed by triangles (\blacktriangledown) when $P \leq 0.05$. All results were processed using GraphPad Prism 10.0.2.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experiment design: Red arrows indicate the oral infection of sheep with third-stage larvae L3, brown arrows indicate faeces collection and spraying with DMSO, 1 μ M ABZ or 5 μ M ABZ, grey horizontal arrows indicate cultivation of third-stage larvae (L3) of generation G1 or G2. Control groups are blue-coloured, groups exposed to lower ABZs dose (1 μ M) are yellow-coloured, and groups exposed to higher ABZs dose (5 μ M) are green-coloured. Grey vertical arrows highlight the qPCR analysis.

3. Results

3.1. The effect of ABZs presence during larval development on DME expression in G1 L3

The contact of larvae during development with sub-lethal doses of ABZs altered the expression of almost all tested DMEs (see Fig. 2). The most increased expression induced by ABZs in both concentrations was observed in the case of *ugt26a2*, whereas the expression of *ugt365a1*, *pgp11* and *pgp13* were the most reduced in G1 ABZ1 and G1 ABZ5 groups in comparison to control (G1 DMSO). In addition, the higher dose of ABZs (ABZ5) led to the induction of *ugt368b1*.

3.2. The effect of ABZs presence during larval development on DME expression in G1 adults

The infective L3 of *H. contortus* unexposed or exposed to ABZs during development (groups G1 DMSO, G1 ABZ1 and G1 ABZ5) were used for the infection of 3 lambs. Six weeks post-infection, the *H. contortus* adults were isolated from the abomasum. The expression of selected DMEs was analysed in females and males separately. The expression levels were compared among the adults, which were in contact with ABZs during larval development (groups ABZ1 and ABZ5) and adults developed from larvae without contact with ABZs (group DMSO). The results are presented in Fig. 3(A and B).

Interestingly, exposure of larvae to ABZs significantly elevated the expression of *ugt365a1* and *ugt371a1* and decreased the expression of *ugt24b1*, *ugt365b5* and *pgp11* in both male and female adults. In females of group ABZ5, the expression of *ugt368a1* and *368a2* was also decreased in comparison to controls.

3.3. The effect of ABZs presence during the development of larvae G1 on DME expression in G2 L3

In order to determine whether the ABZs-induced changes in the expression of DMEs in G1 L3 are maintained in G2 L3 that were not exposed to ABZs during development, the expression level of DMEs was compared between the G1 control group (G1 DMSO), ABZs exposed groups (G1 ABZ1, G1 ABZ5) and the second generation groups of larvae without ABZs exposition (G2 ABZ1-DMSO, G2 ABZ5-DMSO).

The results (see Fig. 4) showed three different trends in the expression of selected DMEs; some changes in expression evoked by ABZs in G1 L3 remained in G2 L3, e.g., decreased expression of *ugt365a1* and *pgp13* evoked by both ABZ concentrations, or increased expression of *ugt26a2*

and *ugt368b1* evoked by ABZ5. The expression of some genes (e.g., *ugt368a1*, *pgp11*) altered by ABZ in G1 L3 returned to the normal (i.e. to the level comparable with controls) in G2 L3. Surprisingly, some genes with no ABZs-changed expression in the G1 L3 exhibited significantly increased expression in the second generation (G2 L3), which was not exposed to ABZs. This concerns *ugt24b1* and *ugt365b5* in larvae affected by both concentrations of ABZs, *ugt368a2* in ABZ1 groups and *pgp9.2* in ABZ5 groups.

3.4. The effect of ABZs presence during the larval development on DME expression in G2 L3

The expressions of selected DMEs were analysed and compared in four groups of G2 larvae: G2 ABZ1-DMSO, G2 ABZ1-ABZ1, G2 ABZ5-DMSO, and G2 ABZ5-ABZ5 (see Fig. 5).

Concerning lower ABZs dose, a significant decrease of *ugt24b1*, *ugt365b5*, *ugt368a1*, and *ugt368a2* expression was observed. On the other hand, expression of only *ugt365a1* was elevated by ABZ1. A higher dose of ABZs diminished the expression of *pgp11* and *pgp13*.

4. Discussion

Pharmacotherapy using anthelmintics represents the major strategy against helminthiasis in humans and animals; however, anthelmintics have become important environmental contaminants as their huge amount has entered the environment for more than half a century. Due to their wide use and distribution, anthelmintics impact both the terrestrial and aquatic environments. Moreover, anthelmintics persist in the environment for a long time with only limited degradation and limited possibilities of their remediation (Mooney et al., 2021; Navratilova et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021; Zrnčić et al., 2014). Our previous study proved an undesirable permeation of ABZ and its metabolites from sheep excrements into the soil, plants (used as fodder) and subsequently to other sheep in real agricultural conditions (Navratilova et al., 2021). ABZ circulation causes the permanent exposition of the ecosystems and food chain to the drug and might negatively affect the non-target organisms. As most anthelmintics do not exhibit acute toxicity (at environmentally relevant concentrations), their negative impact is negligible and underestimated and the information about these effects remains scarce (Vokřal et al., 2023).

Besides non-target organisms, traces of ABZ and its metabolites in the environment might also affect parasite helminth and contribute to drug resistance development. As the resistance of helminths to anthelmintics is now a worldwide problem complicating the pharmacotherapy of

Fig. 2. The relative expression of selected *ugt* and *pgp* genes in *H. contortus* L3 exposed to 1 μ M or 5 μ M ABZ during development (groups G1 ABZ1 and G1 ABZ5) compared to control groups of L3 exposed to DMSO only (G1 DMSO) group. Triangles indicates a significant difference between respective groups and the DMSO control (set to 1) at $P \leq 0.05$, $N = 4$.

Fig. 3. The relative expression of selected *ugt* and *pgp* genes in *H. contortus* females (A) and males (B) obtained from sheep infected with L3 exposed to DMSO only (control group DMSO) or 1 μ M ABZs or 5 μ M ABZs during development (groups ABZ1 and ABZ5). Triangles indicates a significant difference between respective groups and the DMSO control (set to 1) at $P \leq 0.05$, $N = 4$.

helminthiasis in human and veterinary medicine, the mechanisms of resistance and factors contributing to resistance development have been studied intensively. In parasitic nematodes, two enzyme families, UGTs and Pgps have attracted the attention as possible participants in drug resistance. Both enzyme families play important roles in defence of nematodes against anthelmintics and other toxic xenobiotics, as well as in signalling pathways and eobiotic metabolism (Dimunova et al., 2022b; Langeland et al., 2021). In our previous studies, we revealed significant changes in the expression of some *ugt* and *pgp* genes in all developmental stages of drug-resistant in comparison to the drug-sensitive strain of *H. contortus* (Kellerová et al., 2020a; Matouskova et al., 2018). Moreover, the 4-h exposure of L3 of *H. contortus* to 1 μ M ABZ increased expression of *ugt368a2* and *ugt371a1* (Kellerová et al., 2020a), and the 24-h exposure of *H. contortus* adults *ex vivo* to 0.1 or 1 μ M ABZ altered expression of several *ugt* and *pgp* genes (Kellerová et al., 2020b). In addition, altered expression of several *ugt* genes was revealed in *H. contortus* adults *in vivo* exposed to fodder plants grown in the field fertilised with the dung from ABZ-treated animals (Dimunova et al., 2022a). However, the information about intrageneration and intergeneration stability of these ABZ-evoked changes was lacking.

Therefore, the present study was designed to simulate the contact of

juvenile stages of *H. contortus* with traces of ABZ and its transformation products (ABZs) in the environment with the aim to follow up the changes in the expression of selected *ugt* and *pgp* genes in L3 and their persistence in adults of the first generation and L3 of the second generation. During the development of the second generation, the exposure to ABZs was repeated (or not) to compare the response of two generations of L3 when only the first or both were in contact with ABZs. The *ugt* and *pgp* genes, which expression levels were measured, were selected from those, which were inducible by ABZ (or monepantel or ivermectin) in *H. contortus* and/or upregulated in *H. contortus* resistant strains (David et al., 2018; Dimunová et al., 2022; Kellerová et al., 2020a, 2020b; Raza et al., 2016)

Juvenile stages of *H. contortus* might be exposed to traces of ABZs in pastures where ABZ-treated animals are grazing and ABZs are excreted with faeces. The ABZ concentration of 7.7 μ g per gram of ovine faeces was the maximal concentration (C_{max}) that reached 9 h after single-dose treatment of lambs with ABZ, but during the first hour after treatment, they are only traces (ng per gram) of ABZs in faeces which cannot be lethal for *H. contortus* eggs (Prchal et al., 2016). In addition, the faeces with ABZs might be mixed with faeces containing eggs in pastures, e.g., faeces excreted before deworming. Moreover, ABZs from faeces spread

Fig. 4. The intergeneration comparison of relative expression of selected *ugt* and *pgp* genes in *H. contortus* L3. (A) The first generation of L3 was exposed to 1 μM ABZs during development (group G1 ABZ1), while the second generation of L3 were exposed only to DMSO during development (group G2 ABZ1-DMSO). (B) The first generation of L3 was exposed to 5 μM ABZs during development (group G1 ABZ5), while the second generation of L3 were exposed only to DMSO during development (group G2 ABZ5-DMSO). Triangles indicates a significant difference between respective groups and the first generation of larvae without ABZs exposition (G1 DMSO; set to 1) at $P \leq 0.05$, $N = 4$.

and persist in the environment, e.g., ABZ metabolites were detected in soil (up to 25 cm from faeces) for three months when the experiment ended (Navrátilová et al., 2023). In the present study, the faeces collected with *H. contortus*-infected lambs were immediately sprayed once with a solution of 1 μM or 5 μM ABZ. The volume of 5 mL was used for 500 g of faeces, i.e., the concentrations were 2.65 ng (or 13.25 ng) per gram of faeces, which correspond to concentrations found in faeces of ABZ-treated lambs up to one hour after treatment (Prchal et al., 2016). The faeces contain approx. 4 000 eggs per gram, i.e., 2.65 ng (or 13.25 ng) of ABZ affected approx. 4 000 eggs. These concentrations are much lower to decrease the hatching of eggs as EC_{50} for ABZ was 0.82 μg per 1 000 eggs (Silva et al., 2021) i.e. 3.28 μg per 4 000 eggs. As ABZ is spontaneously oxidized in aerobic conditions and bacteria as well as juvenile stages of *H. contortus* can metabolise ABZ (Kellerová et al., 2020a; Lagos et al., 2021), the formation and presence of ABZ metabolites is sure. The ABZs was present in the faeces during the development of larvae (8 days) to simulate the situation in the environment. The larvae L3 exposed or unexposed (as controls) to ABZs during

development were used to infect the lambs to obtain the adults and second generation of L3. In L3 of first generation, in the adult females and males and in the L3 of the second generation, the expression of selected *ugts* and *pgps* genes were analysed and compared. The genes with different expression in drug-sensitive and drug-resistant strain of *H. contortus* and the genes with expression affected by ABZs exposure in previous studies (Dimunova et al., 2022a; Kellerová et al., 2020a; Matouskova et al., 2018) were selected for the analysis with focus on intra- and intergeneration stability of these changes.

The results showed that the exposition of juvenile stages to traces of ABZs induced expression of *ugt26a2* and *ugt368b1* in L3 and this induced expression was passed to the second generation of L3 even though they were not exposed to ABZs during development. This finding clearly demonstrates the intergeneration persistence of these changes. The exposition of the second generation to ABZs did not further alter the expression of these two genes. In previous studies, constitutive expression of *ugt26a2* and *ugt368b1* was higher in adults of drug-resistant strain(s) of *H. contortus* (Matouskova et al., 2018) and contact of

Fig. 5. The effect of ABZs exposition during larvae development on the relative expression of selected *ugt* and *pgp* genes in the second generation (G2) of *H. contortus* L3. (A) Larvae G2 were exposed to DMSO only (control groups) or 1 μ M ABZ during development in faeces from the lambs infected with the first generation of L3, which were exposed to ABZs 1 μ M during larvae development. (B) Larvae G2 were exposed to DMSO only (control groups) or 5 μ M ABZs during development in faeces from the lambs infected with the first generation of L3, which were exposed to ABZs 5 μ M during larvae development. Triangles indicates a significant difference between the treated group and the DMSO control (set to 1) at $P \leq 0.05$, $N = 4$.

adults with ABZs-induced expression of these genes (Dimunova et al., 2022a; Kellerová et al., 2020b).

In the present study, the exposition of juvenile stages to traces of ABZs significantly induced expression of *ugt365a1* and *ugt371a1* in adult females and males of *H. contortus*, although decreased expression of *ugt365a1* and unaffected expression of *ugt371a1* was observed in L3. However, decreased expression of *ugt365a1* was also observed in the second generation of L3, indicating the intergeneration stability of this change. Interestingly, the exposure of the second generation of juvenile stages to ABZs evoked an increased expression of *ugt365a1* in L3 of the second generation. Previously, direct exposure of adults to ABZs caused induction of both *ugt365a1* and *ugt371a1* genes. Besides, *ugt371a1* exhibited increased expression in larvae incubated in ABZ solution (1 μ M) for 4 h (Kellerová et al., 2020a).

The expression of four genes, namely *ugt24b1*, *ugt368a1*, *pgp11*, and

pgp13, was decreased in L3 that were exposed to traces of ABZs during development. ABZs-evoked downregulation of *pgp11* and *pgp13* was a little bit surprising as these genes were upregulated by monepantel, ivermectin and oxfendazole in *H. contortus* (David et al., 2018; Raza et al., 2016). Three of ABZs-induced changes (decreased expression of *ugt24b1*, *ugt368a1*, *pgp11*) were preserved in adulthood, while one change (decreased expression of *pgp13*) passed into the next generation of L3, which was not exposed to ABZs during development. However, repeated contact of the second generation of juvenile stages with ABZs decreased again the expression of all these genes in L3 of the second generation. Surprisingly, the expression of *ugt24b1* was markedly increased (12 times) in the second generation of L3 (which were not exposed to ABZs during development) if the first generation of larvae were in contact with ABZs during development. When constitutive expression of UGTs was compared in adults of drug-sensitive and

drug-resistant strains of *H. contortus*, expression of *ugt24b1*, *ugt368a1* was higher in the drug-resistant strain (Matoušková et al., 2018).

Interesting profiles of expression changes were also observed in the case of *ugt365b5* and *ugt368a2*. Their expression was decreased in adults that were in contact with ABZs during juvenile stages but increased in the second generation of larvae L3 that were not exposed to ABZs during development. Moreover, the exposition of the second generation of juvenile stages to ABZs decreased the expression of these genes in L3 of the second generation, although the ABZs-exposure of juvenile stages of the first generation did not alter the expression of both genes in L3 of the first generation. Concerning *ugt365b5*, their constitutive expression in adults was lower in the resistant than in the sensitive strain of *H. contortus* (Matoušková et al., 2018), but *in vivo* exposition of adults of sensitive strain to traces of ABZ and its metabolites induced the expression of this gene (Dimunova et al., 2022a). Concerning *ugt368a2*, induction of these genes by ABZ was observed in adults *ex vivo* and also in L3 in laboratory conditions (Kellerová et al., 2020a, 2020b).

In conclusion, all results mentioned above clearly demonstrate that the contact of free-living stages of parasitic nematodes with ABZs in the environment evoked changes in the expression of certain *ugt* and *pgp* genes, with some of these changes being intra- and inter-generation stable. The contribution of these changes to drug resistance development might be only speculated, as the ABZs-evoked changes were followed up only for two generations, which is not enough for observation of any signs of decreased drug susceptibility (Sarai et al., 2015). Moreover, only some of ABZs-evoked changes represented upregulation of *ugt* and *pgp* genes (which could result in accelerated ABZ deactivation and efflux). ABZ-evoked downregulation of *ugt* and *pgp* genes may seem surprising, but it is necessary to take into mind, that many UGT and P-gp isoforms are probably not involved in drug metabolism but have a distinct role in the endogenous metabolism of nematodes, like in other organisms. ABZ-induced decrease in the expression of certain isoforms may thus represent some changes in endogenous metabolism that may contribute to better nematode tolerance. Unfortunately, present information on the role of UGTs and Pgps in parasitic nematodes is very limited. Nevertheless, our results highlighted the importance of the refugia concept in breeding management (Hodgkinson et al., 2019), which limits the exposure of free-living stages of helminths to excreted anthelmintics on the pasture.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Karolína Šterbová: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation. **Linh Nguyen Thuy:** Investigation, Data curation. **Martin Žofka:** Validation, Formal analysis. **Petra Matoušková:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation. **Josef Krátký:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Lenka Skálová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Lenka Skalova reports was provided by Charles University Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove. Lenka Skalova reports a relationship with Charles University that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or

personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2025.144281>.

Data availability

The data will be available at Zenodo repository.

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